

A Binary Logistic Regression Model for Assessing the Effect of Farmers-Herders Crisis on Postharvest Losses of Crops in Benue State

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ABSTRACT

In this research work, the binary logistic regression model was employed to examine the socio-demographic characteristics of affected farmers, identify the causes of the crisis, and quantify its impact on postharvest losses. Primary data were collected from 450 farmers in Agatu, Guma and Logo local government areas using structured questionnaires and key informant interviews. A random sampling technique was used to ensure representativeness. The study reveals that farming in Benue State is male-dominated (80.9%), with most farmers aged 41-50 years (32.9%) and having primary or secondary education (76.2%). The majority (77.2%) is married, with extensive farming experience and 45.6% have farmed for 11-20 years. Household sizes are relatively large, with 58.7% having 6-10 members, and 83.3% of farmers own land. Despite this, most farmers operate small to medium-sized farms (1-10 hectares, 88.2%), and 35.8% earn between ₦200,000-₦300,000 annually, indicating financial vulnerability. Analysis of the crisis's causes indicates that overgrazing ($\bar{x} = 4.78$), indiscriminate bush burning ($\bar{x} = 4.78$), historical grudges ($\bar{x} = 4.75$), political influence ($\bar{x} = 4.73$), desertification ($\bar{x} = 4.70$), poverty ($\bar{x} = 4.70$), reprisal attacks ($\bar{x} = 4.69$), and poor cattle control ($\bar{x} = 4.76$) are the most significant triggers of conflict. Other contributing factors include cultural and religious differences, cattle theft, and scarcity of grazing land. The logistic regression model confirms that the crisis significantly increases postharvest losses. Farmers experiencing crop destruction are 10.83 times more likely to suffer losses ($\text{Exp}(B) = 10.83$, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, loss of lives and properties ($\text{Exp}(B) = 6.28$), reduction in crop quality ($\text{Exp}(B) = 5.57$), infrastructural damages ($\text{Exp}(B) = 5.87$), increased food poverty ($\text{Exp}(B) = 5.16$), and displacement of homes and farmlands ($\text{Exp}(B) = 4.10$) significantly raise the likelihood of postharvest losses. However, security improvements ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.37$), economic support for farmers ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.46$), and conflict resolution mechanisms ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.19$) significantly mitigate losses. The model exhibits a high predictive accuracy of 99.8%,

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with a Nagelkerke R^2 of 0.993, confirming its robustness. The Hosmer-Lemeshow test ($p = 0.998$) further validates the model's reliability. The study recommends the urgent need for conflict resolution initiatives, economic empowerment programmes for affected farmers, improved security measures, and sustainable land-use policies to address the crisis's impact on postharvest losses and ensure the stability of agricultural livelihoods in Benue State.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Improving Nigeria's food production and security are fundamental objectives of the country's agricultural development program. Thus, National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP) and Operation Feed the Nation (OFN) targets securing enough nutritious food for all citizenry (Abubakar, Gambo, and Umar, 2021). The crisis situation as orchestrated by several attack/terrorist groups in Benue state and Nigeria at large has depressed food production and security, thus threatening the very core of such national agricultural programmers. Farmer-herder's crisis is an emergent situation in the nation's food production and security structure, casting a shadow over the nation's agricultural productivity and stability (Udosen, 2021). This age long crisis informed by the dire competition over scarce resources including: land and water, has resulted in widespread displacement of farming communities and disruption of agricultural activities. The continuous clashes have not only led to the loss of lives and property but have also disrupted the traditional farming practices that form the backbone of Nigeria's agrarian economy.

According to Webb, *et al.* (2018), one of persistent problem through human existence is hunger and malnutrition which are the greatest challenges facing the world. This is because all human being whether rich or poor needs food to survive; as food gives adequate nutrient required for healthy growth, a feeling of comfort, and satisfaction. To enjoy a healthy lifestyle therefore adequate food security is required because it ensures balanced dieting, which is needed for growth, energy, and longevity. However, the Food and Agriculture Organization, (2014) reported that the several countries suffering extreme poverty and depth of hunger (less than 300 kilocalories per day) are in Africa. The recent emphasis on alleviating hunger, reducing malnutrition, and the serious consequences of food insecurity on the poor, calls for investigation on food problems in African countries.

The menace posed by herdsmen in different communities they migrate to for purposes of grazing their cattle is becoming very frightening. They constitute major security challenges to their host communities. The tendency towards engaging the land and farm owners of the sites they graze their cattle is increasing by the day as they update their armory with highly sophisticated weapons. This is the prevailing security challenge in some communities and states in Nigeria. The herdsmen have become an imminent danger which Nigeria cannot continue to ignore. The disastrous consequence of their activities is not only on national

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security but equally a major bane to food availability and sustainability. However, discourse on herdsmen and farmers conflict in contemporary Nigeria has largely been done without emphasis on its implication to food security. The major crises that may escalate in the near future as a result of these conflicts are shortage in food production and the insecurity of lives and property.

The United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (UNFAO, 2008) defined the definition emphasis that there are four criteria which determines food security. They are: the physical availability of food, economic access to these foods, appropriate utilization, and stability. These four qualities must be met before a system can be described as food secure. On the other hand, the World Food Summit Plan, (2012) defined food security as when all people at all times have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs.

Nigeria has experienced a lot of socio-economic crises which can be traced to the herdsmen and farmers crises in the country. Some of these crises have economic, political, social, and environmental dimensions. Each of these dimensions has affected the country at different times within the last ten decades. There have been series of herdsmen and farmers crises which have affected every area and sector of Nigeria especially the economic and political sector. Dambazzu (2007), opined that the herdsmen and farmers crises is not the only major crises the country has experienced, others include ethnic and religious conflicts, insurgency, terrorism etc. Just like every country of the world with one form of crises or the other, the herdsmen and farmers conflict has caused a great disparity between the people. The crises have over the years made the country underdeveloped. As a result of the conflicts, Nigeria has been tagged the poverty capital of the world (Emeka, 2016). The tag came about because of the destruction of lives, properties and farmlands. The rate and intensity of the crises has further increased in some parts of the country especially the north central political zone.

Ironically, the herdsmen and farmers crises now have a new dimension to it. The crises now have a religious undertone. The crises have pitched Christianity and Islam against each other. This has affected the age long peaceful coexistence and communal relationship between the predominantly Christian south and predominantly Muslim north. This is more evident in mono-religious settlements like the Agatu, Guma, Logo people of Benue state. As a result of these clashes, most places that are traditionally peaceful are now hotspot of violence and conflicts. These clashes have had devastating effect on the relationship between the people of the area.

The effect of herdsmen/famers crisis on food security in Nigeria has resulted to worst situation, this is because all the various measures put in place by the government to manage the situation have not achieved the expected outcome. The continuous crisis has also shown that it is difficult to achieve Goal 2 of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) in the

country as the farmers continue to experience post-harvest losses due to the herdsmen attack. It is against this background that this study seeks to assess the effect of farmers-herders crisis on postharvest losses of crops in Benue state of Nigeria using binary logistic regression model.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Method of Data Collection

Primary data was collected from farmers in three local government areas of Benue state through personal interviews with the use of a standardized structured questionnaire. The local government areas include Agatu, Guma and Logo local government areas representing the three agricultural zones in Benue state. The choice of the study location was based on the simple fact that the selected three LGAs are the major local governments in Benue State where the herdsmen-farmers crisis is of great concern. A total of 450 questionnaires were administered to farmers from the selected LGAs and because it was face to face interview with the farmers all the 450 questionnaires were retained. A simple random sampling technique was used for this purpose because every farmer in the study area had an equal chance and probability of being interviewed. The questionnaire used for the interview sought information on socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, causes of herdsmen-farmers conflicts farming information as well as the impact of crisis on postharvest losses of crops and socio-economic sustenance of farmers in the study area. Interviews were done in the local language in order not to create any language barrier. Key informant interviews were also conducted to gather technical information on farming, postharvest losses of crops and herdsmen-farmers crisis in order to verify and validate the accuracy of some information supplied by farmers.

2.2 Methods of Data Analysis

The following statistical tools are employed in the analysis of data in this work.

2.2.1 Binary logistic regression model

Binary logistic regression is a statistical method used for modeling the relationship between a binary dependent variable and one or more independent variables. The dependent variable takes only two possible outcomes, typically coded as 0 and 1, representing categories such as success/failure, presence/absence, or affected/unaffected. The model estimates the probability of an event occurring by applying the logistic function to a linear combination of independent variables (Hosmer, Lemeshow & Sturdivant, 2013).

A binary choice of the i th individual is represented by a random variable y_i that takes on the value of 0 if a farmer did not experience postharvest losses of crops due to herdsmen-farmers crisis and 1 if the farmer experiences postharvest losses of crops due to the crisis. Where p_i is the probability that y_i takes on the value 1, and then $1 - p_i$ is the probability that that y_i is 0. This can be written using the probability function for y_i as

$$F(y_i) = p_i^{y_i}(1 - p_i)^{1-y_i}, \quad y_i = 0, 1 \quad (1)$$

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and

$$y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{with probability } p \\ 0 & \text{with probability } 1 - p \end{cases}$$

In this case, $y = 1$ when the respondent experiences postharvest losses of crops due to herdsman-farmers crisis and $y = 0$ when the respondent did not experience postharvest losses of crops due to the herdsman-farmers crisis.

A logistic regression model is presented below. Linear probability models are constrained between 0 and 1, whereas linear functions are inherently unbounded. Therefore, to ensure the probability is no longer restricted, a transformation is necessary (Allison, 2012). As noted by Allison (2012), converting probability into an odds ratio eliminates the upper bound, while applying the logarithm to the odds removes the lower bound. For k explanatory variables and $i = 1, \dots, T$ individuals, the logistic model is given as:

$$\log \left[\frac{p_i}{1 - p_i} \right] = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik} \tag{2}$$

where p_i is the probability that y_i takes on the value 1, and then $1 - p_i$ is the probability that that y_i is 0. Solving the logit equation for p_i , we have

$$p_i = \frac{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})}{1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})} \tag{3}$$

Exp (x) is the exponential function, equal to e^x , where e is the exponential constant equivalent to 2.71828 (Allison, 2012). Using the property $\log(e^x) = x$, we can further simplify the last equation:

$$p_i = \frac{1}{(1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}))} \tag{4}$$

The estimated β coefficient of the equation, however, does not directly represent the marginal effects of the independent variables of the probability that a farmer is affected by the herdsman-farmers crisis or incurs postharvest losses of crops.

Generally, the outcome in multiple logistic regression analysis is often coded as 0 or 1, where 1 indicates that the outcome of interest is present, and 0 indicates that the outcome of interest is absent. If we define p as the probability that the outcome is 1, the multiple logistic regression model can be written as follows:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik})}{(1 + \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}))} \tag{5}$$

where p_i is the expected probability that the outcome is present; x_1 through x_k are distinct independent variables; and β_0 through β_k are the regression coefficients.

The binary logistic regression model for assessing the effect of the Farmers-Herders crisis on postharvest losses of crops in Benue State, Nigeria, can be formulated as follows:

$$\log\left(\frac{P(Y = 1)}{1 - P(Y = 1)}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CD + \beta_2 LLP + \beta_3 RQC + \beta_4 DFI + \beta_5 IFP + \beta_6 ID + \beta_7 DHF + \beta_8 HPFI + \beta_9 APS + \beta_{10} TK + \beta_{11} SI + \beta_{12} ESF + \beta_{13} CRM + \varepsilon \quad (6)$$

where

$P(Y = 1)$ represents the probability that a farmer experiences postharvest losses due to the Farmers-Herders crisis.

$\log\left(\frac{P(Y=1)}{1-P(Y=1)}\right)$ is the log-odds (logit) of experiencing postharvest losses.

CD = Crop destruction

LLP = Loss of lives and properties

RQC = Reduction in quality of crops

DFI = Decreased farmer's income

IFP = Increased food poverty

ID = Infrastructural damages

DHF = Displaced homes and farmlands

$HPFI$ = High prices of food items

APS = Agricultural product scarcity

TK = Terrorism and kidnapping

SI = Security improvements

ESF = Economic support for farmers

CRM = Conflict resolution mechanisms

β_0 is the intercept of the model

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_{13}$ are the coefficients representing the effect of each predictor variable on the likelihood of postharvest losses

ε is the error term.

This model estimates the impact of various factors related to the Farmers-Herders crisis on postharvest losses, with the odds ratio $\exp(\beta_i)$ indicating the likelihood of losses occurring due to each predictor variable.

2.2.2 Assumptions of logistic regression model

- i. Logistic regression does not require a linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables.
- ii. The dependent variable must be binary (having only two categories).

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- iii. The independent variables do not need to be normally distributed, linearly related, or have equal variance across groups.
- iv. The categories must be mutually exclusive, meaning each case belongs to only one group, and every case must be assigned to a group.
- v. A larger sample size is required compared to linear regression, as maximum likelihood estimation performs better with larger datasets.

2.2.3 Maximum likelihood estimation of logistic regression model

The Logistics regression model coefficients tell us the relation between a dummy dependent variable and continuous or/and categorical independent variables. In logistic regression the coefficients estimates expect to have optimal values. This is done with the maximum likelihood estimation method which helps to find the set of parameters for which the probability of observed data is largest (Allison, 2012). From equation (1) we can observe that each y_i represents a binomial count in the i^{th} population, the maximum likelihood equation comes from the probability distribution of dependent variable which is Y , the joint probability density function of Y is:

$$f(y|\beta) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{y_i(n_i - y_i)!} p_i^{y_i} (1 - p_i)^{n_i - y_i} \tag{7}$$

Let us describe some of the notations; the combination function $C(n_i, y_i)$ is the number of different ways to arrange y_i successes from n_i trials that give as the part $\frac{n_i}{y_i(n_i - y_i)!}$. For any one of these trials the probability of success is p_i , similarly the probability of $n_i - y_i$ failures is $(1 - p_i)^{n_i - y_i}$. The likelihood function is almost the same as the probability density function except the parameters of the function are reversed. Thus, the likelihood function uses fixed value for Y . So the function looks

$$L(\beta|y) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{y_i(n_i - y_i)!} p_i^{y_i} (1 - p_i)^{n_i - y_i} \tag{8}$$

Rearranging equation (1) gives

$$\left(\frac{p_i}{1 - p_i} \right) = e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}} \tag{9}$$

After solving for and using equation (9) the equation to be maximized can be written as:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n \left(e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}} \right)^{y_i} \left(1 - \frac{e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}}}{1 + e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}}} \right)^{n_i} \tag{10}$$

And taking the logarithm of both sides, the equation can be written as

$$L(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_k) = \ln L(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_k)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i \ln p_i + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - p_i)) \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i \ln \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-y_i) \ln \frac{1}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 L(\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_k) &= \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i \ln(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}) \\
 &\quad - (1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik}}))
 \end{aligned}$$

We take the derivative with respect to each β and set equal to zero to get the critical points of the log likelihood function

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{\partial}{\partial \beta_j} \sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij} = x_{ij} \\
 \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta_j} &= \sum_{i=1}^n y_i x_{ij} - n_i \cdot \frac{1}{1 + e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}}} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta_j} (1 + e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}}) = \dots \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^n y_i x_{ij} - n_i p_i x_{ij} = 0 \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

The estimate for β can be found by setting each of the $k + 1$ equations at equation (11) equal to zero and solve for each. This solution gives us a critical point either a maximum or minimum and if the matrix of second partial derivatives is negative definite it will be maximum (Allison, 2012).

This matrix also forms the variance-covariance matrix of the parameter estimates. It can be found by differentiating each of the $k + 1$ equations in equation (11) for the second time with respect to each, so the form of the matrix of second partial derivative is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2 L(\beta)}{\partial \beta_j \partial \beta_{j'}} &= \frac{\partial L(\beta)}{\partial \beta_{j'}} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i x_{ij} - n_i p_i x_{ij} = \frac{\partial L(\beta)}{\partial \beta_{j'}} \sum_{i=1}^n -n_i p_i x_{ij} \\
 &= - \sum_{i=1}^n n_i p_i x_{ij} \frac{\partial L(\beta)}{\partial \beta_{j'}} \left(\frac{e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}}}{1 + e^{\sum_{j=0}^k \beta_j x_{ij}}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

After using some general rules for differentiation we will get

$$\frac{\partial^2 L(\beta)}{\partial \beta_j \partial \beta_{j'}} = - \sum_{i=1}^n n_i x_{ij} p_i (1 - p_i) x_{ij} \tag{12}$$

Putting equation (12) equal to zero results in $k + 1$ nonlinear equations with $k + 1$ unknown variables. But solving a system of nonlinear equations is difficult, so that the solution must be numerically estimated by using an iterative process. Accordingly we need to apply Iterative solution using Newton-Raphson method. We want to find the roots for (11) simultaneously but it is better to use matrix notation. It is possible to write (11) as $l'(\beta)$ and let $\beta^{(0)}$ represent a vector of initial approximations for each β_j , the initial step of Newton-Raphson can be expressed as:

$$\beta^{(1)} = \beta^{(0)} + [-l''(\beta^{(0)})]^{-1} \cdot l'(\beta^{(0)})$$

By using matrix multiplication, we can see that

$$l'(\beta) = X^T(y - \mu)$$

Where μ is a column vector of length N with elements $\mu_i = n_i p_i$ and $l'(\beta)$ will be a column vector of length $k + 1$ with elements $\frac{\partial l(\beta)}{\partial \beta_j}$. We also have

$$l''(\beta) = X^T W X$$

where W is a square matrix of order N with diagonal elements $n_i p_i (1 - n_i p_i)$ and zero everywhere else, then $l''(\beta)$, described using matrix multiplication as above, is a $k + 1 \times k + 1$ square matrix with elements $\frac{\partial^2 L(\beta)}{\partial \beta_j \partial \beta_{j'}}$ (Allison, 2012). So we can write the initial step Newton-Raphson as

$$\beta^{(1)} = \beta^{(0)} + (X^T W X)^{-1} \cdot X^T(y - \mu)$$

This iteration will continue until there is no change between the elements of β from one to the next iteration. Then the maximum likelihood estimates will converge.

2.2.4 Odds and Odds Ratio

Odds are the ratio of probability of an event occurring divided by the probability of it not occurring (Allison, 2012). The odds ratio (OR) is a measure of how strongly an event is associated with exposure. The odds ratio is a ratio of two sets of odds: the odds of the event occurring in an exposed group versus the odds of the event occurring in a non-exposed group. Odds ratios commonly are used to report case-control studies. The odds ratio helps identify how likely an exposure is to lead to a specific event. The larger the odds ratio, the higher odds that the event will occur with exposure. Odds ratios smaller than one imply the event has fewer odds of happening with the exposure (Greenfield *et al.*, 2008). Mathematically

$$\text{Odds} = \frac{\text{Pr (success)}}{\text{Pr (failure)}} = \frac{p}{1 - p} \tag{13}$$

where p is the probability of success and $1 - p$ is the probability of failure.

Odds always have values greater than zero and if odds value is larger than one it means that success will occur more likely than failure. Odds ratio, as the name indicates, is the ratio of two Odds. Mathematically

$$\text{Odds Ratio} = \frac{p_1}{1 - p_1} / \frac{p_2}{1 - p_2} \quad (14)$$

Here, p_1 and p_2 refer to the probability of success in group 1 and group 2 respectively.

If the odds ratio value is greater than one it indicates that the odds of the outcome in group 1 is larger than in group 2. Thus, subjects in group 1 are more likely to have success than subjects in group 2. If the odds ratio is less than the value one, expect that the reverse will occur and if it equal to one subjects of odds of both in group 1 and group 2 will equally likely occur (Greenfield *et al.*, 2008).

For binary logistic regression, the odds of success are:

$$\frac{p}{1 - p} = \exp(x\beta)$$

The odds increase multiplicatively by $\exp(\beta_j)$ for every one-unit increase in x_j . When there is just a single predictor, x , the odds of success are:

$$\frac{p}{1 - p} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)$$

By increasing x by one unit, the odds ratio becomes

$$\text{OR} = \frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1(x + 1))}{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)} = \exp(\beta_1) \quad (15)$$

2.3 Determination of Model Adequacy

For diagnostic check and determination of model adequacy, we employ the following statistical tools.

2.3.1 Pseudo R^2 measure in logistic regression

For a logistic regression which is fitted by the method of maximum likelihood, there are several choices of pseudo $-R^2$. Cox and Snell (1989) and by Magee (1990) independently proposed the pseudo R^2 given by:

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{L(\tilde{\theta})}{L(\hat{\theta})} \right)^{2/n} \quad (16)$$

where $L(\tilde{\theta})$ is the maximized likelihood of the model with only the intercept (the null model), $L(\hat{\theta})$ is the maximized likelihood of the estimated model (the model with a given set of all predictors) and n is the sample size. It can easily be rewritten as:

$$R_{CS}^2 = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{2}{n} (\ln(L(\tilde{\theta})) - \ln(L(\hat{\theta}))) \right] = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{D}{n} \right] \quad (17)$$

where D is the test statistic of the likelihood ratio test.

Nagelkerke (1991) noted that the Cox and Snell pseudo R^2 statistic has the following properties:

- i. It is consistent with the classical coefficient of determination when both can be computed;
- ii. Its value is maximized by the maximum likelihood estimation of a model;
- iii. It is asymptotically independent of the sample size;
- iv. The interpretation is the proportion of the variation explained by the model
- v. The values are between 0 and 1, with 0 denoting that model does not explain any variation and 1 denoting that it perfectly explains the observed variation;
- vi. It does not have any unit.

However, in the case of a logistic model, where $L(\hat{\theta})$ cannot be greater than 1, R^2 is between 0 and $R_{max}^2 = 1 - (L(\tilde{\theta}))^{2/n}$: thus, Nagelkerke (1991) suggested the possibility to define a scaled R^2 as:

$$R_N^2 = \frac{1 - \left(\frac{L(\tilde{\theta})}{L(\hat{\theta})} \right)^{2/n}}{1 - L(\tilde{\theta})^{2/n}} \quad (18)$$

where $L(\tilde{\theta})$, $L(\hat{\theta})$ and n are as earlier defined. The Nagelkerke pseudo R^2 can also be given as

$$R_N^2 = \frac{R_{CS}^2}{R_{max}^2} \text{ and } R_{max}^2 = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{2}{n} L(\tilde{\theta}) \right] \quad (19)$$

The Nagelkerke measure adjusts the Cox and Snell measure for the maximum value so that 1 can be achieved.

2.3.2 The likelihood ratio test

The likelihood-ratio test assesses the goodness of fit of two competing statistical models based on the ratio of their likelihoods, specifically one found by maximization over the entire parameter space and another found after imposing some constraint. If the constraint (i.e., the null hypothesis) is supported by the observed data, the two likelihoods should not differ by more than sampling error (Li and Bagu, 2019). Thus the likelihood-ratio test tests whether this ratio is significantly different from one, or equivalently whether its natural logarithm is significantly different from zero. The statistic is given by

$$\lambda_{LR} = -2 \ln \left(\frac{L(\tilde{\theta})}{L(\hat{\theta})} \right) = -2 [\ln L(\tilde{\theta}) - \ln L(\hat{\theta})] = -2 [L(\tilde{\theta}) - L(\hat{\theta})] \quad (20)$$

where $L(\tilde{\theta})$ is the maximum value of the likelihood function of the null (intercept only) model and $L(\hat{\theta})$ is the maximum value of the likelihood function of the estimated (the full) model.

The estimated (full) model has all the parameters of interest and the null model has only the intercept (Hosmer *et al.*, 2013). The likelihood ratio test tests the following pair of hypothesis:

$H_0: \beta_i = 0$ (the dropped variables are not significant contributors to predicting the dependent variable) versus

$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$ (the dropped variables are important in predicting the dependent variable).

2.3.3 Omnibus test of model coefficients

Like the likelihood ratio test statistic, the Omnibus test statistic is a measure of the overall model fit. The Omnibus test tests the following pair of hypothesis:

$H_0: \beta_i = 0$ (All coefficients of the independent variables are equal to zero) versus

$H_1: \beta_i \neq 0$ (There is at least one coefficient of an independent variable that is not equal to zero).

The null hypothesis is rejected when the p-value of the Omnibus test statistic is less than 0.05 (level of significance). A significant test statistic implies that the logistic regression model can be used to fit the data.

2.3.4 The Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness of fit test

The **Hosmer-Lemeshow** (HL) test is a goodness of fit test for logistic regression, especially for risk prediction models. A goodness of fit test tells us how well our data fits the model. Specifically, the HL test calculates if the observed event rates match the expected event rates in population subgroups. The test is only used for binary response variables (a variable with two outcomes like alive or dead, yes or no).

Data is first regrouped by ordering the predicted probabilities and forming the number of groups, g . The Hosmer-Lemeshow test statistic is calculated with the following formula (Hosmer *et al.*, 2013):

$$G_{HL}^2 = \sum_{j=1}^g \frac{(O_j - E_j)^2}{E_j(1 - E_j/n_j)} \sim \chi_{g-2}^2 \quad (21)$$

where

χ_{n-2}^2 = Chi-squared with $g - 2$ degree of freedom;

n_j = number of observations in the j^{th} group;

O_j = number of observed cases in the j^{th} group;

E_j = number of expected cases in the j^{th} group;

The output of the HL test returns χ^2 value (a Hosmer-Lemeshow chi-squared) and p – *value* (e.g. $Pr > \chi^2$). Small p-values mean that the model is a poor fit for the data. A good fit model will have a small HL test statistic and a p-value that is greater than 0.05 (the significance level).

2.3.5 Classification Table

A classification table gauges the predictive accuracy of a multivariate logistic regression model. The method involves cross classifying the dependent variable y with the categorical variable emanating from the fitted logistic probabilities (\hat{y}). The percentage of successes that have been correctly classified as success is called sensitivity of the model while the percentage of failures that have been correctly classified as failure is called specificity of the model. The failures that are incorrectly classified as success are referred to as false positive and the successes that are incorrectly classified as failures are referred to as false negative (Sharma, 1996). A typical classification table is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Classification Table

Predicted	Obese		Percentage Correct
	No (failure)	Yes (success)	
No (failure)	a	b	$\frac{a}{a + b} \times 100$
Obese			
Yes (success)	c	d	$\frac{d}{c + d} \times 100$
Overall Percentage			$\frac{a + d}{a + b + c + d} \times 100$

In Table 1, sensitivity of the model = $d/c + d \times 100$, specificity of the model = $a/a + b \times 100$. Higher specificity and sensitivity are an indication of a good fit of the model. The classification table is used for data validation. According to Kutner *et al.* (2005) if a model fitting sample produces the same prediction error rate as the validation sample, then the fitted model is reliable.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents includes gender, age, educational qualifications, years of farming experience, and marital status. The detailed results are presented in Table 2. To understand the land ownership status, farm size, household structure, and economic conditions of farmers affected by the farmers-herders crisis in Benue State, Nigeria. The result reported in Table 3 highlight the distribution of these key characteristics. The result of socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents reported in Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents are male farmers (80.9%), indicating that farming in Benue State is male-dominated. This could be due to cultural norms, land ownership structures, and labour demands in agriculture. The relatively lower percentage of female farmers (19.1%) suggests that women may be more engaged in subsistence farming or other agricultural support roles. The age distribution of respondents shows that the majority of farmers fall within the 41-50 years age bracket (32.9%), followed closely by those aged 31-40 years (26.2%) and 51-70 years (25.3%). This suggests that middle-aged and older individuals are more actively engaged in farming. The low participation of younger individuals (15.6%) may indicate rural-urban migration or a shift towards other economic opportunities outside farming.

Table 2: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Respondent's Characteristics		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	364	80.9
	Female	86	19.1
	Total	450	100
Age (in years)	18-30	70	15.6
	31-40	118	26.2
	41-50	148	32.9
	51-70	114	25.3
	Total	450	100
Educational Qualification	None	15	3.3
	Primary	140	31.1
	Secondary	203	45.1
	Tertiary	92	20.5
Total	450	100	
Years of Farming Experience	1-10	98	21.7
	11-20	205	45.6
	21+	147	32.7

	Total	450	100
Marital Status	Single	60	13.3
	Married	347	77.2
	Widowed	29	6.4
	Divorced	14	3.1
	Total	450	100

Source: Researchers' Computation from field work, 2025.

The educational qualification of respondents shows that the majority of respondents (76.2%) have at least a primary or secondary education, indicating a moderate literacy level among farmers. Only 3.3% have no formal education, which suggests that most farmers can read and understand agricultural extension materials or policies. The 20.5% with tertiary education may include those engaged in agribusiness or educated individuals involved in farming due to economic challenges. Farming is dominated by experienced individuals, with 45.6% having 11-20 years of experience and 32.7% farming for over 21 years. This suggests that most respondents are seasoned farmers, potentially more vulnerable to the economic and security effects of the crisis. The 21.7% with less than 10 years of farming experience might include younger farmers or individuals transitioning into agriculture. The majority of farmers (77.2%) are married, which suggests that farming is largely practiced by family households in Benue State. This highlights the economic and social vulnerability of families affected by the farmers-herders crisis. The presence of widowed (6.4%) and divorced (3.1%) respondents indicates that conflict-related violence may have contributed to family disruptions.

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents reveals a farming population that is predominantly male, middle-aged, moderately educated, and highly experienced. These characteristics suggest that conflict-induced disruptions significantly affect households that rely on agriculture for survival.

Table 3: Land Ownership Status, Farm Size, Household Headship, Size and Income of Respondents

Respondent's Characteristics			Frequency	Percentage
Land Ownership Status	Yes	Yes	375	83.3
		No	75	16.7
	Total	450	100	
Farm Size (in hectares)	1-5	1-5	110	24.4
		6-10	287	63.8
		11+	53	11.8
	Total	450	100	
Household Headship	Yes	365	81.1	
	No	85	18.9	

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	Total		450	100
Household Size (Members of Household)	1-5		138	30.7
	6-10		264	58.7
	11+		48	10.6
	Total		450	100
Household Income (₦)	<100000		76	16.9
	100000-200000		115	25.6
	200000-300000		161	35.8
	>300000		98	21.7
	Total		450	100

Source: Researchers' Computation from field work, 2025.

The result of Table 3 shows that the majority of farmers (83.3%) own land, indicating that land tenure security is relatively high among respondents. However, the 16.7% who do not own land may be vulnerable to displacement or lease-related conflicts. The farmers-herders crisis could further threaten land tenure stability for both groups. Most farmers (63.8%) operate on medium-sized farms (6-10 hectares), while 24.4% have small farms (1-5 hectares). A smaller percentage (11.8%) own large farms (>11 hectares). Farmers with larger landholdings may be more vulnerable to destruction of farmlands during crises, whereas smallholder farmers may struggle with productivity and resilience against losses. A significant 81.1% of respondents are household heads, reinforcing that farming is family-driven and central to household survival. This implies that disruptions caused by conflicts affect entire family units rather than just individuals.

The majority of farmers (58.7%) live in large households (6-10 members), while 30.7% have smaller households (1-5 members). A smaller proportion (10.6%) has very large families (11+ members). Larger household sizes indicate higher dependency ratios, meaning that postharvest losses due to conflicts could have severe food security implications for these families. The majority of respondents (35.8%) earn between ₦200,000 - ₦300,000 per year, followed by 25.6% earning ₦100,000 - ₦200,000. About 16.9% earn less than ₦100,000, indicating high poverty levels among some farming households. Only 21.7% earn above ₦300,000, showing that a small proportion of farmers are financially well-off. Given that farming is the primary source of income, conflict-induced losses could significantly exacerbate poverty and economic hardship, especially for those earning below ₦200,000 annually.

The findings suggest that land ownership and farming are central to household stability in Benue State. However, large household sizes, modest farm sizes, and low incomes make farmers highly vulnerable to economic distress and food insecurity when affected by conflict. These results highlight the urgent need for conflict resolution, livelihood support,

and economic empowerment programs to mitigate the crisis’s impact on farming communities.

3.2 Result of the Causes of Herdsmen-Farmers Conflicts

To investigate the causes of herdsmen-farmers crisis in the study area, farmers were asked to indicate the extent to which they agree or disagree that the following factors contribute to herdsmen-farmers conflicts on a 5-point rating scale of (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly Agree). The Means and modes of the responses are computed and reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Result of the Causes of Herdsmen-Farmers Conflicts

Item	Mean (\bar{x})	Mode
Indiscriminate bush burning	4.78	5
Cultural differences	4.34	4
Scarcity of forage	3.91	4
Poor land use planning	2.62	2
Poor control of cattle	4.76	5
Rape and sexual harassment of women by herders	2.57	2
Religious differences	4.21	4
Reprisal attacks	4.69	5
Poverty	4.70	4
Historical grudges	4.75	5
Cattle theft (cow rustling)	4.17	4
Indiscriminate livestock defecation	2.42	2
Pollution of water sources by livestock	3.90	4
Scarcity of grazing fields	3.94	4
Overgrazing	4.78	5
Political reasons	4.73	5
Desertification	4.70	5

From the result of the causes of herdsmen-farmers crisis reported in Table 4, the major causes of the crisis are those with mean ≥ 4.5 and mode = 5. These factors were strongly agreed upon as primary causes of the conflict, with high mean scores and a mode of 5 (Strongly Agree). For example, indiscriminate bush burning ($\bar{x} = 4.78$, mode = 5) indicates that uncontrolled burning of bushes destroys grazing fields, forcing herders to move into farmlands, sparking conflicts; poor control of cattle ($\bar{x} = 4.76$, mode = 5) indicates that lack of proper cattle management leads to destruction of farmlands, which is a major trigger for disputes; reprisal attacks ($\bar{x} = 4.69$, mode = 5) shows that retaliatory violence exacerbates the crisis, creating a cycle of conflicts between farmers and herders.

Also, historical grudges ($\bar{x} = 4.75$, mode = 5) indicates that long-standing animosities between communities fuel continuous clashes; political reasons ($\bar{x} = 4.73$, mode = 5) shows that political influences, ethnic tensions, and policy failures aggravate the conflict; overgrazing ($\bar{x} = 4.78$, mode = 5) indicates that overuse of available grazing land depletes resources, leading to encroachment on farmlands. Desertification ($\bar{x} = 4.70$, mode = 5) indicates that environmental degradation, such as drought and desert encroachment, reduces available grazing land, escalating tensions; poverty ($\bar{x} = 4.70$, mode = 4) reveals that economic hardship among both farmers and herders intensifies competition for limited resources.

The significant causes of the crisis are those with mean between 4.0 - 4.49 and mode = 4. These factors were widely agreed upon as contributing to the conflict. For example, cultural differences ($\bar{x} = 4.34$, mode = 4) indicates that differences in values, customs, and lifestyles between farmers and herders create misunderstandings; also religious differences ($\bar{x} = 4.21$, mode = 4) shows that conflicts are sometimes fueled by religious divides, further straining relationships; cattle theft (cow rustling) ($\bar{x} = 4.17$, mode = 4) reveals that theft of cattle by criminal groups or community members leads to violent confrontations.

Similarly, scarcity of grazing fields ($\bar{x} = 3.94$, mode = 4) shows that limited pastureland pushes herders into farmlands, increasing disputes; scarcity of forage ($\bar{x} = 3.91$, mode = 4) similar to grazing field scarcity, lack of adequate feed for livestock forces encroachment on farmlands. Pollution of water sources by livestock ($\bar{x} = 3.90$, mode = 4) shows that contamination of rivers, lakes and streams by cattle leads to disputes between farmers and herders.

The less significant causes are those with mean < 3.0 and mode = 2. These factors were disagreed upon or received mixed responses, suggesting they are less significant. For instance, Poor land use planning ($\bar{x} = 2.62$, mode = 2) indicates that while land use planning is an issue, farmers do not see it as a primary cause of conflicts. Also, rape and sexual harassment by herders ($\bar{x} = 2.57$, mode = 2) reveals that though rape cases exist, this factor was not widely recognized as a major cause. Indiscriminate livestock defecation ($\bar{x} = 2.42$, mode = 2), this was the least agreed upon factor, suggesting that it is not a significant driver of conflict.

Overall, environmental factors (bush burning, overgrazing, desertification, scarcity of grazing land and forage) are major triggers of the crisis. Social and political factors (historical grudges, religious differences, political influence) play a critical role in escalating conflicts. Economic factors (poverty, cattle theft) contribute significantly to clashes. Security concerns (reprisal attacks, poor cattle control) intensify the crisis whereas rape, poor land use planning, and livestock defecation were not widely regarded as major causes.

3.3 Impact of Crisis on Postharvest Losses of Crops and Socio-Economic Sustenance of Farmers

The farmers-herders crisis in Benue State, Nigeria, has significantly impacted agricultural productivity, particularly in terms of postharvest losses. This study employs a binary logistic regression model to assess the effect of this crisis on postharvest losses. The analysis seeks to determine whether the crisis significantly increases the likelihood of postharvest losses among farmers in the region.

3.3.1 Binary logistic regression model

This study employs a binary logistic regression model to assess the effect of the crisis on postharvest losses, where the dependent variable is whether a farmer is a victim of the crisis (yes = 1, no = 0). Table 5 presents the case processing summary, which provides an overview of the dataset used for the analysis, including the number of cases included and excluded due to missing values.

Table 6 presents the Classification table for the null model, which serves as a baseline for evaluating the model’s predictive ability before introducing independent variables. The null model (also called the intercept-only model) assumes that all predictions are based on the most frequent category of the outcome variable without considering any predictors.

Table 5: Case Processing Summary

Unweighted Cases		N	Percent
Selected cases	Included in Analysis	450	92.6
	Missing Cases	36	7.4
	Total	486	100.0
Unselected Cases		0	0.0
Total		486	100.0

The result of Table 5 shows that out of a total of 486 cases (farmers surveyed), 450 cases (92.6%) were included in the analysis, meaning they had complete data required for the binary logistic regression model, 36 cases (7.4%) were missing values, meaning they were excluded from the analysis. Missing cases could arise due to incomplete responses, data entry errors, or other factors, 0 unselected cases (0.0%) indicate that all valid cases were considered, and none were removed for reasons such as sampling criteria. The dataset has a high level of completeness (92.6% inclusion), which suggests that the analysis is based on a robust sample size, reducing potential biases from missing data.

The result of Table 6 compares the observed values (actual cases of victimization) with the predicted values (what the null model predicts) based solely on the most frequent

category. The model predicts that all farmers are victims of the crisis (i.e., it assigns all cases to the “Yes” category), 62 farmers were observed as not victims, but the model incorrectly predicted them as victims (0% correct classification for “No” cases), 388 farmers were observed as victims, and the model correctly classified all of them (100% correct classification for “Yes” cases). The overall percentage correct is 86.2%, which reflects the imbalance in the data, where most respondents (388 out of 450) reported being victims of the crisis.

The null model provides a benchmark for evaluating the predictive power of the logistic regression model when predictors are introduced. Since it classifies all cases as victims, it does not offer real predictive power but merely reflects the dominant category in the dataset.

Table 6: Classification Table for the Null Model

	Observed		Predicted		Percentage correct
			VICTIM OF FARMER HERDER CRISIS	OF FARMER CRISIS	
Step 0	VICTIM OF FARMER HERDER CRISIS		No	Yes	
	No	Yes	0	62	0.0
			0	388	100.0
	Overall percentage				86.2

a. Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is 0.500

Table 7 presents the constant-only (null) model, which serves as a baseline before incorporating independent variables. This model includes only the intercept (constant) and assumes that all cases fall into a single category based on the most frequent outcome. It helps determine whether the outcome variable significantly differs from random chance.

The B coefficient for the constant only model reported in Table 7 is 1.834. This represents the log-odds of a farmer experiencing postharvest losses when no predictor variables are included. The Wald statistic value of 179.783 tests whether the constant is significantly different from zero. A high Wald statistic here indicates strong statistical significance. The p-value of 0.000 indicates that the constant only model is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$), meaning the likelihood of postharvest losses is significantly different from random chance. The Exp(B) value is 6.258, indicating that the odds of experiencing postharvest losses are 6.258 times higher than not experiencing them when no predictor variables are considered.

The results of the constant only model indicate that, in the absence of predictor variables, farmers are significantly more likely to experience postharvest losses due to the

crisis. However, the model does not yet explain why these losses occur. The next step is to introduce independent variables to assess their individual contributions to postharvest losses and improve model accuracy.

Table 7: The Constant Only (Null) Model

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	p-value	Exp(B)
Step 0 Constant	1.834	0.137	179.783	1	0.000	6.258

Table 8 presents the Omnibus tests of model coefficients, which evaluates whether the inclusion of independent variables in the model significantly improves its predictive ability over the null (constant-only) model.

The Omnibus test result reported in Table 8 consists of three components: step, block, and model. Each tests the overall significance of the logistic regression model by comparing it to the constant-only model. The Chi-square value of 356.999 indicates the difference in model fit between the null model (constant-only) and the new model with predictor variables. A higher chi-square value suggests a better model fit. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates that the model with predictors significantly improves over the null model, meaning at least one of the independent variables has a meaningful impact on postharvest losses. The results confirm that the logistic regression model with predictor variables provides a significantly better fit than the null model. This suggests that independent variables contribute to the likelihood of postharvest losses in the context of the farmers-herders crisis.

Table 9 presents the model summary, which provides key statistics that evaluate the goodness-of-fit of the logistic regression model. These measures help determine how well the model explains variations in postharvest losses.

Table 8: Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	Df	p-value
Step 1	Step	356.999	10	0.000
	Block	356.999	10	0.000
	Model	356.999	10	0.000

Table 9: The Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	3.819 ^a	0.548	0.993

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 20 because parameter estimates changed by less than 0.001.

The result of Table 9 provides a summary of -2 Log Likelihood, Cox and Snell pseudo R Square and Nagelkerke R Square statistics. The -2 log likelihood (-2LL) is a measure of how well the model fits the data. A lower value of -2 log likelihood of 3.819 indicates a better fit. The drastic reduction from the null model suggests that the inclusion of predictor variables has significantly improved the model's explanatory power. The Cox & Snell pseudo R Square value of 0.548 suggests that approximately 54.8% of the variation in postharvest losses can be explained by the predictor variables in the model. The Nagelkerke R Square is a modified version of Cox & Snell R^2 that adjusts for its limitations. Nagelkerke R Square value of 0.993 (99.3%) indicates an excellent model fit, meaning the included variables explain nearly all the variation in postharvest losses due to the farmers-herders crisis.

The high Nagelkerke R^2 value (0.993) suggests that the logistic regression model provides a strong explanation for the likelihood of postharvest losses in the study area. The significant reduction in -2LL further supports that the model has improved substantially compared to the null model. These findings imply that the crisis, alongside other predictor variables, has a strong influence on postharvest losses.

Table 10 presents the Hosmer and Lemeshow test, which is a key goodness-of-fit test used to evaluate how well the logistic regression model describes the observed data. It assesses whether there is a significant difference between the predicted and actual values of the dependent variable.

Table 10: Hosmer and Lemeshow Test for the Full Model

Step	Chi-Square	Df	P-value
1	0.427	5	0.998

The Chi-Square test statistic is used to evaluate the fit of the model. A lower value of 0.427 indicates a better model fit, meaning the model’s predicted probabilities align closely with the observed data. A p-value greater than 0.05 (specifically 0.998) suggests that there is no significant difference between the observed and predicted values, meaning the model fits the data well. Since the Chi-Square p-value is very high ($0.998 > 0.05$), the test confirms that the logistic regression model provides a good fit to the data. This means that the model’s predictions closely match the actual outcomes, reinforcing the validity of the selected predictor variables in explaining postharvest losses due to the farmers-herders crisis.

Table 11 presents the Classification Table for the full model, which evaluates the predictive accuracy of the logistic regression model after incorporating independent variables. It compares the observed outcomes (actual cases) with the predicted outcomes (model-generated classifications).

Table 11: Classification Table for the Full Model

	Observed	Predicted		
		VICTIM OF FARMER HERDER CRISIS	Percentage Correct	
		No	Yes	
Step 1	VICTIM OF FARMER HERDER CRISIS	No	Yes	
		62	0	100.0
		1	387	99.7
	Overall Percentage			99.8

- a. Constant is included in the model
- b. The cut value is 0.500

The classification table assesses how well the model predicts whether a farmer is a victim of the farmers-herders crisis, based on the model’s probability estimates. Out of 62 actual “No” cases (farmers not affected by the crisis), the model correctly classified all 62 cases (100.0% accuracy). Out of 388 actual “Yes” cases (farmers affected by the crisis), the model correctly predicted 387 cases and misclassified only 1 case (99.7% accuracy). The model achieved a total classification accuracy of 99.8%, meaning it almost perfectly distinguishes between farmers who experienced postharvest losses due to the crisis and those who did not.

The very high accuracy (99.8%) suggests that the logistic regression model provides a strong predictive capability for determining the impact of the farmers-herders crisis on postharvest losses. The sharp improvement from the null model (86.2%) further confirms that the inclusion of predictor variables significantly enhances the model’s performance.

3.3.2 Parameter Estimates of the Full Binary Logistic Model

Table 12 presents the parameter estimates of the full binary logistic model, which provides deeper understanding into the influence of different predictor variables on the likelihood of experiencing postharvest losses due to the crisis. The key statistics include the B coefficients, standard errors (S.E.), Wald test values, degrees of freedom (df), p-values, odds ratios (Exp(B)), and confidence intervals (95% C.I. for Exp(B)).

Table 12: Parameter Estimates of the Full Binary Logistic Model

Variable	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	P-value	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for Exp(B)	
							Lower	Upper
CD	2.832	0.319	78.814	1	0.000	10.827	6.316	13.763
LLP	1.838	0.257	51.148	1	0.000	6.284	3.412	9.682
RQC	1.718	0.453	14.383	1	0.000	5.573	2.997	8.418
DFI	0.498	0.119	17.513	1	0.000	1.645	0.774	3.615
IFP	1.641	0.446	13.538	1	0.000	5.160	2.982	7.887
ID	1.770	0.938	3.561	1	0.009	5.871	3.007	8.451
DHF	1.410	0.698	4.081	1	0.006	4.096	2.163	7.557
HPFI	0.861	0.259	11.051	1	0.000	2.366	0.987	4.415
APS	0.508	0.286	3.153	1	0.017	1.662	0.786	3.627
TK	0.633	0.245	6.675	1	0.001	1.883	0.875	3.717
SI	-0.985	0.225	19.165	1	0.000	0.373	0.097	0.577
ESF	-0.773	0.187	17.087	1	0.000	0.462	0.087	0.609
CRM	-1.655	0.173	91.517	1	0.000	0.191	0.075	0.372

Constant	2.453	0.514	1	0.000	11.623
					22.776

Note: a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: CD=Crop Destruction, LLP=Loss of lives and Properties, RQC= Reduction in Quality of Crops, DFI=Decreased Farmer’s Income, IFP=Increased Food Poverty, ID=Infrastructural Damages, DHF=Displaced Homes and Farmlands, HPFI=High Prices of Food Items, APS=Agricultural Product Scarcity, TK=Terrorism and Kidnapping, SI=Security improvements, ESF=Economic Support for Farmers, CRM=Conflict Resolution Mechanisms.

From the result of Table 12, each independent variable represents a factor contributing to postharvest losses. The B coefficient (log-odds), Exp(B) (odds ratio), and p-values help determine their significance and impact on postharvest losses of crops in the study area. Variables with Exp(B) > 1 indicate an increased likelihood of postharvest losses due to the crisis while variables with Exp(B) < 1 indicate a protective effect, reducing the likelihood of postharvest losses.

The slope coefficient of crop destruction (CD) is positively related to postharvest loss of crops and statistically significant at 5% level of significance (Exp(B) = 10.827, 95% CI [6.316, 13.763], p = 0.000). Farmers experiencing crop destruction are 10.83 times more likely to suffer postharvest losses than those who do not. The effect is highly significant (p < 0.05) and the confidence interval shows a high degree of certainty in this estimate. The slope coefficient of loss of lives and properties (LLP) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level (Exp(B) = 6.284, 95% CI [3.412, 9.682], p = 0.000). Affected farmers have a 6.28 times higher likelihood of experiencing postharvest losses of crops than unaffected farmers. In other words, loss of lives and properties increases the likelihood of postharvest losses of crops by 6.28 times. This suggests that displacement and instability directly impact food security.

The slope coefficient of reduction in quality of crops (RQC) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level (Exp(B) = 5.573, 95% CI [2.997, 8.418], p = 0.000). Farmers experiencing a reduction in crop quality are 5.57 times more likely to have postharvest losses. In other words, lower crop quality increases postharvest losses by 5.57 times. The slope coefficient of decreased farmer’s income (DFI) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level (Exp(B) = 1.645, 95% CI [0.774, 3.615], p = 0.000). Farmers with lower incomes are 1.65 times more likely to suffer postharvest losses. Lower income reduces farmers’ capacity to invest in storage, transportation, and security, thereby increasing postharvest losses.

The slope coefficient of increased food poverty (IFP) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 5.160$, 95% CI [2.982, 7.887], $p = 0.000$). Increased food poverty raises postharvest loss risks by 5.16 times. Households facing increased food poverty are 5.16 times more likely to experience postharvest losses, emphasizing the economic toll of the crisis. The slope coefficient of infrastructural damages (ID) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 5.871$, 95% CI [3.007, 8.451], $p = 0.009$). Poor roads, storage, and transport increase losses by 5.87 times. In other words, damage to roads, storage facilities, and irrigation systems raises the likelihood of postharvest losses by 5.87 times.

The slope coefficient of displaced homes and farmlands (DHF) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 4.096$, 95% CI [2.163, 7.557], $p = 0.006$). Displacement leads to a 4.10 times higher likelihood of postharvest losses of crops. Displacement of farmers significantly increases postharvest losses, as it disrupts farming activities and market access. The slope coefficient of high prices of food items (HPFI) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 2.366$, 95% CI [0.987, 4.415], $p = 0.000$). Farmers facing higher food prices are 2.37 times more likely to experience losses. Farmers facing higher food prices are 2.37 times more likely to suffer postharvest losses. This suggests market instability due to crisis-related disruptions.

The slope coefficient of agricultural product scarcity (APS) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 1.662$, 95% CI [0.786, 3.627], $p = 0.017$). Scarcity of agricultural products increases postharvest losses by 1.66 times, likely due to disrupted supply chains. The slope coefficient of terrorism and kidnapping (TK) is also positively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 1.883$, 95% CI [0.875, 3.717], $p = 0.001$). The presence of terrorism and kidnapping raises the likelihood of postharvest losses by 1.88 times, as it discourages farming activities.

The slope coefficient of security improvements (SI) is negatively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.373$, 95% CI [0.097, 0.577], $p = 0.000$). Improved security reduces postharvest losses by 63% ($1 - 0.373$). This suggests that better security measures play a crucial role in mitigating losses. The slope coefficient of economic support for farmers (ESF) is negatively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.462$, 95% CI [0.087, 0.609], $p = 0.000$). This implies that economic interventions reduce postharvest losses by 54% ($1 - 0.462$). The slope coefficient of conflict

resolution mechanisms (CRM) is negatively related to postharvest loss of crops in the study area and highly statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 0.191$, 95% CI [0.075, 0.372], $p = 0.000$). This is a strongest protective factor, reducing postharvest losses by 81% ($1 - 0.191$).

The intercept of the binary logistic regression model is positively related to postharvest loss of crops and statistically significant at the 5% level ($\text{Exp}(B) = 11.623$, $p = 0.000$). This intercept represents the baseline log-odds when all other predictors are at zero. A significant intercept suggests that even without the crisis, some level of postharvest loss would still occur.

Overall, the binary logistic regression result revealed that factors like crop destruction, loss of lives and Properties, reduction in quality of crops, decreased farmer's income, increased food poverty, infrastructural damages, displaced homes and farmlands, high prices of food items, agricultural product scarcity, terrorism and kidnapping are associated with the likelihoods of increasing postharvest losses of crops in the study area; whereas security improvements, economic support for farmers and conflict resolution mechanisms significantly reduce postharvest losses, reinforcing the need for policy interventions.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the farmer-herder crisis has a significant impact on postharvest losses in Benue State, Nigeria. The findings highlight the need for conflict resolution initiatives, economic empowerment programs, improved security measures, and sustainable land-use policies to address the crisis's impact on postharvest losses and ensure the stability of agricultural livelihoods in Benue State.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar A., Gambo, J. and Umar, S. (2021). An overview of the effects of some agricultural policies in Nigeria 1960-2020. *Nigerian Agricultural Journal*, 52 (3) 151s
- Allison, P. D. (2012). *Logistic regression using SAS: Theory and application*. Second Edition. Cary, NC: SAS Institute Inc.s
- Cox, D. D., and Snell, E. J. (1989). *The analysis of binary data*. 2nd edition. Chapman and Hall. Pp. 79-83.
- Farmers Herders Conflict in Nigeria Preprint · December 2020 DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16410.88008 CITATION 1 READS 32,097 1 author: Gülşah Gürsoy Philipps University of Marburg
- Food and Agriculture Organization (2014, September 23rd). *The state of food insecurity in the world (SOFI)*.
- Hosmer, D. W., Lemeshow, S. A., and Sturdivant, R. X. (2013). *Applied logistic regression*. 3rd edition. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley. Pp. 103-107.

<https://www.modernghane.com/news/349849/who-are-the-fulani-people-theirorigins.html>.
(Accessed June 9th, 2020).

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Kotikota, S. M., Flores, A., Griffin, R. E., Nyaga, J., Case, J. L., Mugo, R., Seda, A., Adams, E., Limaye, A., & Irwin, D. E. (2019). Statistical characterization of frost zones: Case of tea freeze damage in the Kenyan highlands. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*.

Lee, S. W. (2022). Regression analysis for continuous independent variables in medical research: statistical standard and guideline of Life Cycle Committee. *Life cycle, 2.s*

Li, B., and Babu, G. J. (2019). *A Graduate Course on Statistical Inference*. Springer. Pp. 331

Magee, L. (1990). R^2 measures based on wald and likelihood ratio joint significance tests. *The American Statistician*, 44, 250–253.ss

Nagelkerke, N. J. D. (1991). A note on a general definition of the coefficient of determination. *Biometrika*, 78(3), 691–692.s

Sabouri, S., Hajrasouliha, A., Song, Y., & Greene, W. H. (2020). Logistic regression. In *Basic Quantitative Research Methods for Urban Planners* (pp. 270-304). Routledge.

Udosen, N. M. (2021). Farmers-herders crisis and food security in Nigeria: causes and implications. *European Journal of Political Science Studies*, 5(1).s

Umaru, A. (2021). Causes of farmer-herders conflict in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Webb, P. Stordalen, GA., Singh, S., Wijesinha-Bettoni, R., Shetty, P. & Lartey, A. (2018). Hunger and malnutrition in the 21st century. *Biomedical Journal 13* (361) Doi: 10.1136/bmj.k2238.